

HYBRID THERMOSET COMPOSITES FOR IMPROVING FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the engineering thermoplastic and the rigid nanofiller aim to toughen a brittle epoxy resin without losing the mechanical and thermal properties of this thermoset. The composites of polyethersulfone (PESU), Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) and bisphenol A-based epoxy resin was prepared by mechanical mixing. The influence of PESU and GNPs on the characteristics and properties of epoxy were investigated. For the binary blends of PESU/epoxy, two-phase morphology was observed which PESU-rich phase dispersed in the epoxy matrix. According to the two-phase morphology, the enhancement of fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and fracture energy (G_{Ic}) of the blend was obviously found with PESU content. Fracture surface showed the crack deviation around the thermoplastic phase that is the vital toughening mechanism for the binary blend. In addition, the presence of 0.5 wt% GNPs slightly improved fracture performance of the binary blend. The maximum value of K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} (1.05 MPa.m^{1/2} and 236 J.m⁻² respectively) were investigated at the combination of 10 wt% PESU with 0.5 wt% GNPs loading which were counted as 37 % and 71 % improvement compared with the reference epoxy, respectively. As expected, the glass transition temperature (T_g) and tensile properties of the composites were maintained with the addition of PESU and GNPs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Among the class of thermoset, the epoxy tends to be the most versatile material that covers tremendous applications such as adhesives, coating, electrical devices, and structural composite materials [1,2]. These varieties in usages are due to the outstanding properties in its rigidity, strength, thermal, and chemical resistance. The major drawbacks of thermoset materials are the brittleness and low resistance of crack initiation according to the highly crosslink structure of epoxy [2]. These poor mechanical properties prohibit the use of virgin cured epoxy in high performance application. To overcome those limitations without losing the remarkable properties, the addition of rigid materials such as an engineering thermoplastic and nanofillers have been proposed as a toughened agent to improve the fracture toughness and delay the crack propagation [1,3].

Polyethersulfone (PESU) is a class of high performance engineering thermoplastic that exhibit excellent properties in stiffness and strength with good thermal stability. PESU has been incorporated with epoxy resin not only to improve fracture toughness but also to maintain the mechanical and thermal properties of epoxy in several studies [1,4–12]. It is well known that the characteristic of the blend morphology plays an important role to enhance the toughness mechanism. Both single and two-phase morphology were reported in the literature [1,6,8]. The single-phase morphology is revealed when the formation of interpenetrating polymer network (IPN) was formed [1,13]. The single-phase morphology of PESU/Epoxy blends provides a higher critical-stress-intensity factor or plain-strain fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) than the two-phase morphology system once PESU content is ≤ 10 wt% [1,6,8]. This advantage is due to the shear banding of the matrix [1]. Nevertheless, the preparation of single-phase system is more selective in type of epoxy resin-hardener and curing procedure [1,6]. For the two-phase morphology, PES/Epoxy blends theoretically exhibit the lower critical solution temperature (LSCT) behaviour so the presence of thermoplastic leads to the formation of two-phase morphology via reaction induced phase separation (RIPs) [14,15]. Conventionally, the blends start from the homogenous mixture and then the phase separation occurs during the crosslinking reaction. At small loading of PESU (0 to 15 wt%), the particulate or island-liked structure is generally observed [8,9]. In addition, the co-continuous phase morphology and phase inversion is further developed when at least 20 wt% of PESU

was added [16]. Several toughening mechanisms was proposed for PESU/epoxy blends with two-phase morphology including crack branching, crack pining, crack blunting, crack path deflection and matrix yielding [1,2,8]. Although the co-continuous phase morphology and phase inversion provide better fracture toughness performance. However, the processability is more difficult due to the high viscosity.

Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) are carbon-based nanomaterial which is composed of many layers of graphene sheet [3]. As GNPs provide the superior thermal, electrical and mechanical performances, GNPs/epoxy nanocomposites have been studied in many research areas [3,17–21]. GNPs are also widely used as a reinforced material over single graphene layer. It is due to not only those remarkable properties but also relative low cost [3,22]. The well dispersed of functionalised GNPs in epoxy matrix lead to increase tensile properties and fracture toughness according to a better interfacial interaction between the 2D nanofiller and epoxy matrix [23]. However, the preparation of functionalised GNPs at large amount is impractical. In contrast, GNPs without functionalisation were commonly aggregated as well as GNPs with larger lateral size and aspect ratio [3]. Fortunately, this agglomeration of GNPs resulted in the distinguished toughening mechanism from well dispersed GNPs. The GNPs cluster can effectively deviate the crack while the dispersed GNPs was able to be debonded and pulled out from the matrix [3,17,24].

In this work, both PESU and GNPs were added to toughen a brittle epoxy without losing the mechanical performance and thermal properties of the thermoset. The influence of PESU content on the properties of diamine-cured epoxy was firstly investigated. The blends with the addition of 0.5 wt% GNPs were further studied as the GNPs/PESU/epoxy composites. The hybrid thermoset composites were thermally, mechanically and morphologically characterised as well as the toughening mechanism.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Epoxy resin (Araldite LY564®, EEW of 165 -175 g equivalent⁻¹) and curing agent (Aradur 2954®) was supplied by Huntsman. The ratio of Araldite LY564 to Aradur 2954 was recommended as 100 to 35 by weight. Polyethersulfone or PESU (Ultrason E2020 micro®, 50% of OH-end group with an average weight molecular weight, M_w of 55,000 g mol⁻¹) was kindly received from BASF, Germany. The thermoplastic was dried in a vacuum oven at 140° for 4 hours before used. Dichloromethane and methanol were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. GNPs (Elicarb®, average particle size of 0.5 – 1.0 µm) were kindly provided from Thomas Swan Advanced Materials. GNPs was used as received.

2.2 Preparation of the binary blend and hybrid composites

The blend PESU/epoxy was prepared by mechanical mixing with varying PESU from 0 to 15% by weight. The engineering thermoplastic was directly dispersed in an epoxy resin at room temperature for 90 minutes using mixer speed of 200 rpm. Then stoichiometric ratio of curing agent was added. After mixing and degassing, the liquid composites were cast into a metal mould. The curing and post curing was done in a oven at 80°C for 2 hrs and 140°C for 8 hrs.

To manufacture the hybrid nanocomposites, 0.5 wt% of GNPs were initially dispersed in epoxy resin using a sonication bath for 30 minutes and a high speed shear mixer for 120 minutes at 3000 rpm. Then, PESU (0 to 10 wt%) and diamine curing agent were further added and mixed using an overhead mixer. The uncured hybrid composites were also degassed and cast into a metal mould. The curing and post curing was set with the same curing cycle as described previously.

2.3 Characterisation methods

Dynamic mechanical properties of the blends and hybrid composites were determined using dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) Q800 with a single cantilever clamp from TA instrument on a rectangular specimen of 10 × 35 × 4.5 mm³. The frequency and amplitude was set at 1.0 Hz and 15 µm, respectively. The analysis wasrun from 30°C to 280°C with heating rate of 3.0°C/min. The glass transition temperature (T_g) was determined at the onset of storage modulus (E') using the TA universal analysis software [25].

Tensile test was conducted according to the ASTM D638 with dumbbell specimen type I [26]. The

uniaxial tensile test was performed on an Instron 5969 using a load cell of 10 kN with a cross head speed set at 1.0 mm/min. The atmosphere was controlled at 23 - 25°C and 50% humidity.

Fracture toughness properties of the blend and hybrid composites were examined on single edges notch bending (SENB) test following the ASTM D5045 [27]. The three-point bending configuration was set up on an Instron 5969 using a load cell of 1kN with testing speed of 0.5 mm/min. The specimen dimension of $18 \times 85 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$ was V-notched at the middle by milling machine and then the pre-cracked was introduced by inserting a fresh razor blade. The critical-stress-intensity factor or plain-strain fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and the critical strain energy release rate or fracture energy (G_{Ic}) was calculated using equation 1 and 2, respectively. The test was also under controlled atmosphere similar to the tensile testing.

$$K_{Ic} = (P/BW^{1/2}) f(x) \quad (1)$$

$$G_{Ic} = U/(BW\phi) \quad (2)$$

where P is the applied load, B is the specimen thickness, W is the specimen width, $f(x)$ is a geometry correction factor of specimen which is the function of crack length (a) and W , U is the corrected energy and ϕ is the energy correction factor [27]. The ratio of a/W was between 0.45 to 0.55.

Phase morphology and fractography were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a Tescan MIRA3. For the binary blend system, the samples were etched by a mixed solvent (10 vol% methanol in dichloromethane) to remove PESU [reference]. The surface was coated by Au/Pd (60/40) with a thickness of 3 nm.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 PESU/epoxy blends

The storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ as a function of the temperature of unmodified epoxy and PESU/epoxy blends are shown in Figure 1. The neat cured epoxy (PESU 0) exhibited only one sharp drop of E' as well as a single peak of $\tan \delta$. This showed a transition from glassy to rubbery plateau of an epoxy. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the epoxy was indicated at around 142°C. When the thermoplastic was added into the system, E' at rubbery plateau increased due to glassy state of PESU phase. In addition, the second transition was obviously investigated at about 225 °C corresponding to the T_g of PESU. These two distinguish T_g showed that the two-phase morphology of this blend system is achieved. Table 1 summarised E' and T_g for all samples. The presence of PESU effectively remained both E' and T_g of the epoxy rich phase. This observation was also found in other studied where the blends exhibit two-phase morphology [1,8].

The phase morphology obtained by SEM are illustrated in Figure 2. The two-phase (PESU and epoxy) morphology is clearly observed. Although the uniformly dispersed cluster of PESU varied in size and shape. It is uniformly dispersed in epoxy matrix. Moreover, the PESU cluster became denser with increasing PESU content.

Tensile properties including young's modulus (E_t) and ultimate tensile strength (σ_u) of unmodified epoxy and the PESU/epoxy blends were presented in Table 1. The neat cured epoxy have a modulus (E_t) and ultimate strength (σ_u) of 2.6 GPa and 69 MPa, respectively. As expected, the presence of PESU did not affect the modulus although the strength of PESU modified epoxy decreased up to 20 % compared to the unmodified epoxy.

Figure 1: DMA plot of the unmodified epoxy (a) storage modulus, E' (b) tan delta

Figure 2: Morphology of PESU modified epoxy (a) 0 wt% PESU (b) 5 wt% PESU (c) 10 wt% PESU (d) 15 wt% PESU

The fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and fracture energy (G_{Ic}) of the epoxy and PESU/epoxy blends are summarised in Table 1 and are shown in Figure 3. The measured K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} continuously enhanced with PESU content. At 15 wt% loading of PESU, K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} shows the maximum improvement of 36% and 81%, respectively, compared with an unmodified epoxy. Similar observation of K_{Ic} improvement was also found in the other studies of PESU toughen epoxy having two-phase morphology [1,8]. Mimura et al reported that the enhancement of K_{Ic} showed up to 60% from epoxy modified with 15 wt% PESU [1]. From these results, the relation of these mechanical properties and morphology were considered. The fracture surfaces of all samples are illustrated in Figure 4, the crack propagating from left to right. The fracture surfaces of the unmodified epoxy revealed the smooth crack as shown in Figure 4 (a). In contrast, PESU/epoxy blends exhibit more rough fracture surface due to the appearance of thermoplastic dispersed phase. Figure 4 (b - d) clearly presents the crack path deviation around PESU phase which is the main toughening mechanism for this binary blend. This evidence occurred frequently with higher content of PESU because of the higher cluster density of PESU. Therefore, the fracture performance of epoxy improved with increasing PESU loading.

Sample	E' at 30°C (GPa)	T_{g1} (°C)	T_{g2} (°C)	E_t (GPa)	σ_{max} (MPa)	K_{Ic} (MPa.m ^{1/2})	G_{Ic} (J.m ⁻²)
PESU_0	1.4 ± 0.1	142 ± 1	-	2.6 ± 0.1	69.1 ± 4.8	0.77 ± 0.07	138 ± 17
PESU_5	1.4 ± 0.2	143 ± 1	224 ± 0	2.5 ± 0.0	62.1 ± 6.8	0.90 ± 0.02	162 ± 24
PESU_10	1.4 ± 0.3	144 ± 0	225 ± 2	2.7 ± 0.1	50.2 ± 7.5	0.98 ± 0.03	199 ± 27
PESU_15	1.5 ± 0.2	143 ± 0	224 ± 1	2.7 ± 0.1	55.4 ± 4.1	1.05 ± 0.02	250 ± 36

Table 1: Properties of the unmodified epoxy and PESU/epoxy blends including storage modulus (E'), glass transition temperature (T_g), Young's modulus (E_t), ultimate tensile strength (σ_u), fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and fracture energy (G_{Ic})

Figure 3: Fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and fracture energy (G_{Ic}) of unmodified epoxy and PESU modified epoxy

Figure 4: SEM micrographs of fracture surface (a) 0 wt% PESU (b) 5 wt% PESU (c) 10 wt% PESU (d) 15 wt% PESU

3.2 Hybrid composites of GNPs/PESU/epoxy

From previous section, although the modified epoxy with 15 wt% PESU provided the greatest improvement of K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} , the high viscosity of the blend limited the preparation of hybrid composites. Therefore, only the modified epoxy with 0 – 10 wt% PESU were further studied for the hybrid composites with 0.5 wt% GNPs.

Similar to the studies of PESU/epoxy blends, DMA was used to investigate the dynamic mechanical properties of the GNPs/PESU/epoxy hybrid composites. Figure 5 (a) and (b) compare the influence of GNP on E' and $Tan \delta$ of neat epoxy and binary blends. For the reference epoxy system, the epoxy with 0.5 wt% GNPs exhibits similar behaviour of E' and $Tan \delta$ to the unmodified epoxy which a single T_g was indicated at 142 °C. The hybrid composites show two glass transitions according to T_g of epoxy matrix and PESU dispersed phase at 142°C and 225°C, respectively. The addition of 0.5 wt% GNPs to the system slightly increases E' in glassy state compared to the neat epoxy and binary blends as presented in Table 2. This observation is probably due to the lower chain mobility of epoxy chain and some interaction between 2D nanofiller and epoxy matrix [17].

Tensile properties of GNPs/PESU/epoxy hybrid composites were also evaluated. Figure 6 compares Young's modulus (E_t) and ultimate tensile strength (δ_u) of all samples. The scatter plot of E_t clearly shows that hybrid composites exhibit high stiffness similar to neat cured epoxy with the modulus of 2.5 GPa. In addition, the presence of GNPs do not change δ_u of the epoxy and the blends. Therefore, the slight reduction of tensile strength is dominated by the addition of PESU.

Fracture performances including K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} of the hybrid composites is shown in Table 2. The K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} values of PESU/epoxy blends and GNPs/PESU/epoxy composites are compared and illustrated in Figure 7. All hybrid materials show greater fracture performances which both values of K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} higher than binary system. Although the standard error of both values are large, the similar evidence are also found in the studies of nanofiller toughen epoxy due to the difficulty of testing procedure as well as the poor dispersion of nanofiller [24,28]. The combination of 10 wt% PESU and 0.5 wt% GNPs, K_{Ic}

increases from 0.77 to 1.05 MPa.m^{1/2} while G_{Ic} rose from 138 to 236 J.m⁻². It counts as 37% and 71% of improvement, respectively, compared to the unmodified epoxy. Without GNPs, the modified epoxy with 10 wt% PESU shows only 27% and 44% of enhancement in K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} , respectively.

Figure 5: DMA plot of GNPs/PESU/epoxy composites (a) storage modulus, E' (b) $Tan\ delta$

Sample	E' at 30°C (GPa)	T_{g1} (°C)	T_{g2} (°C)	E_t (GPa)	σ_{max} (MPa)	K_{Ic} (MPa.m ^{1/2})	G_{Ic} (J.m ⁻²)
PESU_0_G0.5	1.5 ± 0.1	142 ± 1	-	2.4 ± 0.2	65.0 ± 3.0	0.83 ± 0.04	171 ± 26
PESU_5_G0.5	1.5 ± 0.1	142 ± 1	224 ± 0	2.5 ± 0.1	62.1 ± 6.8	0.90 ± 0.08	188 ± 23
PESU_10_G0.5	1.5 ± 0.1	144 ± 0	224 ± 2	2.6 ± 0.0	55.4 ± 7.5	1.05 ± 0.04	236 ± 38

Table 2: Properties of the GNPs modified epoxy and GNPs/PESU/epoxy hybrid composites including storage modulus (E'), glass transition temperature (T_g), Young's modulus (E_t), ultimate tensile strength (σ_u), fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and fracture energy (G_{Ic})

Figure 6: Tensile properties of PESU/epoxy blends and GNPs/PESU/epoxy composites

Figure 7: Influence of PESU and GNPs on (a) fracture toughness, K_{Ic} and (b) fracture energy, G_{Ic}

The fracture surface of GNPs modified epoxy and GNPs/PESU/epoxy hybrid composites were observed by SEM and the crack propagation direction is from left to right. With the presence of GNPs, the evidence of crack deviation around the agglomeration of GNPs and GNP debonding from epoxy matrix are investigated as revealed in Figure 8 (a). For the hybrid system, the cracks are additionally deviated by the PESU cluster as explained in previous section. Therefore, the combination of both modifier, PESU and GNPs, promote the fracture toughness through those toughening mechanism as illustrated in Figure 8 (b) and (c).

Figure 8: Fracture surfaces of the hybrid composites (a) PESU 0 wt% with 0.5wt% of GNPs (b) PESU 5 wt% with 0.5 wt% GNPs (c) PESU 15 wt% with 0.5 wt% GNPs

4 CONCLUSION

In summary, the blend of PESU/epoxy and hybrid composites of GNPs/PESU/epoxy were prepared. The binary blend exhibited two-phase morphology, and the clusters of PESU uniformly disperse in epoxy matrix. The presence of PESU lead to an improvement in fracture performance as those PESU clusters effectively deviate the crack propagation. Both fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and fracture energy (G_{Ic}) of PESU/epoxy significantly rise with the PESU content. For hybrid system, the combination of both modifiers, GNPs and PESU, intensively improve the fracture performance of epoxy. At 10 wt% PESU with 0.5 wt% GNPs, K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} are counted as 37% and 71% enhancement, respectively, compared with the reference epoxy. The crack deviations around both PESU phase and GNPs cluster as well as the debonding of nanofiller are found and counted the toughening mechanism for the hybrid system. In addition, the hybrid GNPs/PES/epoxy composites provides thermal and tensile properties comparable to neat cured epoxy with high glass transition temperature (T_g) and the outstanding Young's modulus.

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